

**Fabrication of aramid fiber reinforced composite for
improving the shock wave protection by incorporating
polydimethylsiloxane**

2025. 08. 07.

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- The need of **advanced defensive materials** for military applications

- With the **advancement of science**, an **increasing variety of technologies** are being applied to war

- ✓ **Shock wave**
- ✓ **EMP (electromagnetic pulse)**
- ✓ **Laser**
- ✓ **Radiation**

- The **development of materials** to defend against such attacks has become an **inevitable necessity**

- What is **shock wave**?

- ✓ Wave that occurs when it passes through a fluid **faster than sonic speed**
- ✓ Suddenly **nonlinear, discontinuous** change (temperature, pressure, density)

➔ **Traumatic brain injury (TBI)** → Persistent socioeconomic

- Frictional interaction of micro-domains

- Coating

- Reversible exchange of CAN

- Low T_g of silicon network

- Foam

- Embedded particles

Material	Structure
➤ Polyurea	➤ Coating
➤ Vitrimer	➤ Foam
➤ PDMS	➤ Particles
•	•
•	•

• Coating

• Coating

- ✓ A **wide range** of shock-absorbing materials can be **selected** and can be applied to materials of various shapes and sizes
- ✓ The **adhesion** is **critical**, which makes **strength and durability concerns**

• Foam

• Foam

- ✓ Porous structure is effective for **excellent energy absorption** and **lightweight**
- ✓ The **integrating** foam into the composite and ensuring proper adhesion **can be challenging** and **low in mechanical properties**

Structure

- Coating
- Foam
- Particles
-
-

• Embedded particles

• Embedded particle

- ✓ Particles help **locally disperse and dissipate energy**
- ✓ Proper mixing or dispersion are required, making **production complex**
- ✓ **Poor adhesion** between particles and the matrix cause **debonding**

❖ New structured composite

- Limitation of conventional structure with embedded particle

A.P. Mouritz, Composite Part A 125 (2019), 105502

High shock wave dissipation, Low mechanical properties

Particle content
(Trade-off)

Low shock wave dissipation, High mechanical properties

- Composite with new structure

2nd dosing

High shock wave dissipation through
particle concentrated on the surface

1st dosing

Preserve mechanical properties of FRP

- **Materials**

- ✓ Fiber : Plain woven p-aramid fabric : TW 150 (Taekwang Industrial Co. LTD., Korea)
- ✓ Matrix : Epoxy resin(KFR-120V) +curing agent(KFH-163) (KUKDO Chemical Co. LTD., Korea)
- ✓ Shock waves dissipating materials : **PDMS particles ($>2\mu\text{m}$)** (DOWSIL Industrial Co. LTD., Korea)

- **Process : MDF(multi-drop filling process)**

 Programmable resin dosing system

 Complex shape molding ability

 Minimize viscosity resin flow

 Maintain high mechanical properties

- Optimization of **dispersion** for PDMS/EP suspension

- Optimization of **multi-stage dosing** system for **desired particle distribution**

✓ Experimental measurement of one drop resin volume by **controlling dosing time and pressure**

- Fully distributed AFRP (f-AFRP) fabricating process

1. A precisely quantified suspension was dispensed using MDF process onto the laminated aramid fibers
2. The composite was fabricated via a compression process under a series of curing condition (120 °C, 5 MPa)
3. The **f-AFRP** were prepared with each PDMS wt%, with PDMS **evenly distribution throughout the entire thickness**

- **Surface-only distributed AFRP (s-AFRP) fabricating process**

1. Only **epoxy resin** quantified using MDF process **was dispensed** onto the laminated aramid fibers
2. Subsequently, suspension is distributed using the dosing system and the compression process is carried out
3. The **s-AFRP** were prepared with **same PDMS weight of f-AFRP**, and PDMS was **distributed only on the surface**

- PDMS/epoxy suspension viscosity

f-AFRP	PDMS wt% at f-AFRP	PDMS mass (g)	s-AFRP	PDMS wt% at s-AFRP	PDMS mass (g)
1f-AFRP	1	0.31	1s-AFRP	4.8	0.31
2f-AFRP	2	0.63	2s-AFRP	9.6	0.63
4f-AFRP	4	1.28	4s-AFRP	17.2	1.28
5f-AFRP	5	1.62	5s-AFRP	20.8	1.62

- ✓ The suspension was **well-dispersed** up to **20 wt%** and exhibits shear thinning behaviour → **Uniformity**
- ✓ **Viscosity increases exponentially** with increasing PDMS content **above 20 wt%** → **Processability**

- Distribution of PDMS within AFRP

Optical micrograph(x 50) of cross section of **AFRP** and **AFRP within 2 wt% PDMS**; a) AFRP, b) 2f-AFRP, c) 2s-AFRP, d) Bottom of 2s-AFRP(x100), e) Top of 2s-AFRP(x100), f) Top of 2s-AFRP(x500)

• Shock wave energy dissipation(SWED) measuring system

$$V(t) = \frac{V_{max} + V_{min}}{2} + \frac{V_{max} - V_{min}}{2} \sin(2\pi n(t)) \quad (1)$$

$$u(t) = \frac{\lambda_0 n(t)}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$v(t) = \frac{du}{dt} = 2u_p(t) \quad (3)$$

$$P(t) = \rho_0 (s + cu_p(t)) u_p(t) \quad (4)$$

• Out voltage → Displacement → Free surface velocity → Pressure

✓ Shock wave generation

→ Focused energy rapidly **thermally expands** aluminum, resulting in **generation of shock wave**

✓ Quantification of shock wave pressure

→ Output voltage signal is converted into displacement-time data (**Doppler effect**) ... (1) → (2)

→ **Pressure data** is obtained using the free surface velocity-time data by differentiating over time ... (3) → (4)

- SWED of PDMS/EP film

- ✓ Dissipation shock wave pressure

- **Shock wave energy dissipation(SWED)** = $100(1 - \text{average peak pressure}/\text{initial shock wave pressure})$
- A **50 μm thick film** was evaluated to figure out the **SWED** of the surface layer of the **proposed AFRP**
- An increase in PDMS content within the film led to enhanced SWED (40 wt% PDMS/EP film is similar to 100% PDMS)
- The SWED of epoxy film **with 20 wt% PDMS** increased by **about 35%** compared to using only epoxy

- SWED of PDMS/AFRP

Sample	Average Thickness (μm)	SWED increasing rate (%) (compared to epoxy or AFRP)
20P/epoxy film	50	35
20P/AFRP	500	39

→ Even in AFRP, the measured **average peak pressure was reduced** by the addition of **20 wt% PDMS**

→ The addition of **20 wt% PDMS improved the SWED of FRP** by about **39 %**, showing a similar increase in SWED as in film, so **the effect of PDMS addition could be confirmed indirectly**

- Tensile strength

- The presence of only 5 wt% of PDMS particles content in **f-AFRP** reduces the tensile strength by about **9%**
- Increasing PDMS content of the s-AFRP surface, the tensile strength decreased by about **4%** at **5s-AFRP**
- **The structure of 5s-AFRP is advantageous for maintaining mechanical properties** than 5f-AFRP containing the same amount of PDMS

- Impact strength

- The presence of only 5 wt% of PDMS particles content in **f-AFRP** reduces the impact strength by about **10%**
- As the PDMS content of the **s-AFRP** surface increased, the impact strength **decreased by about 4%** in 2s-AFRP
- The structure of **s-AFRP** is particularly advantageous in maintaining its **impact properties** than f-AFRP containing the same amount of PDMS

- This study proposed **suitable process for effective structure** of future advanced multi-protective equipment
- The s-AFRP was successfully fabricated through **MDF process** with multi-stage dispensing system application
- Despite the increase in PDMS content in the **surface-only distributed AFRP**, **mechanical properties are maintained**
- **Shock wave energy dissipation(SWED) increased exponentially** with increasing PDMS content in **PDMS/EP film** and **PDMS/AFRP**, and SWED increased to **34%** and **39%** in the added 20 wt% PDMS particles, respectively

❖ Thank you for your attention

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**This research was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by Ministry of
Science and ICT (2022M3H4A1A0407)**

Thank you
